

HALAL TOURISM: SERVING MUSLIM TOURISTS

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***Annotation:** The development of halal services in the hospitality and tourism industry is on the rise. According to CrescentRating1, the number of halal tourists worldwide reached 140 million in 2018, and is projected to increase to 230 million by 2026. The global trend of development of the halal hospitality and tourism industry is largely responsible for the increase in publications in this field and the expansion of research topics. For example, the global academic literature reflects the results of studies on the characteristics of Islamic tourism, halal tourism, the needs of Muslim tourists, and the activities of hotels that provide halal services. Halal tourism refers to tourism that is organized in accordance with Islamic norms and is intended for Muslims who want to observe their religious traditions while traveling.*

***Keywords:** community, concepts, hospitality*

The Halal tourism and hospitality sector is of interest to the Russian academic community, as it has obvious prospects for development in the context of multi-ethnic and multi-religious domestic and inbound tourism flows. However, both in Russian- and English-language academic literature, the issue of systematizing existing research areas in this field remains understudied. In fact, there is a lack of a comprehensive understanding of the main trends and areas of research in this field, as well as the main trends in its study, and the concepts and approaches (including interdisciplinary ones) used to analyze the problems.

In addition, they do not consider the hospitality issues from the perspective of bibliometric analysis.

The purpose of this article is to identify the issues and main research directions in the field of halal tourism and hospitality based on the analysis of academic literature. To achieve this goal, the following tasks need to be addressed:

- ◆ establish criteria for selecting and forming a sample for bibliometric analysis of academic publications by foreign authors on halal tourism and hospitality research;
- ◆ determine the bibliometric indicators of works by foreign authors;
- ◆ analyze the problematic field of publications;
- ◆ identify the main concepts and ideas, as well as the context of their use.

As a part of the Islamic world, Uzbekistan was considered the cultural center of Central Asia. During the Eastern Renaissance, the region contributed to the development of Islamic culture, science, and art. The flourishing of Islamic culture in this country occurred during the Middle Ages, specifically from the 9th to the 17th centuries, during the development of the Samanid, Karakhanid, Khwarazmshah dynasties, as well as after the Mongol conquests and the centuries-long decline, with the revival of Islam by Sufi tariqa orders such as Kubrawiya and Naqshbandiya, and the Timurid and Shaybanid dynasties.

Recently, on January 1, 2020, the Uzbek city of Bukhara became the Capital of Islamic Culture. This decision was made at the 9th Conference of Ministers of Culture of the Member States of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC). On December 18, 2019, at the 11th Islamic Conference, three cities - Bukhara (Uzbekistan), Cairo (Egypt), and Bamako (Mali) - were approved as the Capitals of Islamic Culture for 2020. In addition, since 2020, the city of Khiva in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been declared the Turkic Capital of Culture by the Turkic World Organization.

This tradition of announcing three cities from Muslim countries every year is carried out by the Islamic Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (ISESCO). Every year, cities from three Islamic regions - the Arab world, Asia, and Africa - are selected. Previously, in 2007, the Islamic Educational, Scientific and

Cultural Organization (ISESCO) announced the capital city of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, as one of the three capitals of Islamic culture.

As a rule, the capital of Islamic culture is obliged to hold a conference of ministers of culture of Islamic countries, which takes place every two years. Throughout the year, the city chosen as the capital hosts events and activities aimed at presenting its culture and Islamic heritage. This, in turn, contributes to the development of pilgrimage, halal, or Islamic tourism. In the future, the development of halal tourism in Uzbekistan will require addressing certain issues and challenges related to the provision of halal services and facilities.

It is a well-known fact that Uzbekistan is known worldwide for its holy sites and sacred Islamic shrines. As a result, our country is an attractive tourist destination for pilgrims who wish to visit the pilgrimage sites of the great scholars of the Islamic world, the shrines of Sufi sheikhs, and the tombs of saints. Additionally, as a cultural center of Islam, Uzbekistan is home to numerous historical sites, including madrasas, mosques, mausoleums, and Sufi monasteries known as khanaqahs. Tourists can be attracted by the Muslim halal gastronomy and handicrafts of the local population.

Tourism has traditionally been closely linked to religion, which has served as a powerful motivator for travel for centuries. Religious structures, rituals, festivals, and religious events are important tourist attractions for those who follow certain belief systems. Therefore, there is a strong connection between Islam and tourism.

Today, the global Muslim population is over 1.82 billion, and the number of Muslim tourists is increasing every year and is expected to continue growing in the future. The commercial potential of the religious travel market has also been recognized in Muslim countries, and Islamic tourism is now a new tourist destination in the world. Due to the geographical and economic significance of Muslim countries, this tourism is growing daily. Islam encourages tourism for believers to

practice their lives and gain experience and maturity. Islamic tourism has a significant impact on tourists and travelers, as well as on Muslim societies.

Tourism is related to various aspects of Islam. Several researchers have identified the relationship between religion and tourism in various aspects and emphasized that Islam supports various types of tourism activities to enhance religious and social functions. This is a purposeful activity in Islam that aims to achieve physical, social, and spiritual goals. The physical goal leads to a healthy and stress-free life, which in turn allows Muslims to better serve God. Islam encourages Muslims to visit their fellow Muslims, as this contributes to the strengthening of the Muslim community. A spiritual goal strengthens one's submission to God and reinforces one's religious beliefs.

Literatures:

1. M.M., Rakhmatullaeva F.M. Direct foreign investment as a factor in the development of an innovative economy // Actual problems of the humanities and natural sciences, 2014. No. 8-1.
2. Khurramov O.K. How can we use internet marketing in the hotel industry // Modern trends and current issues in the development of tourism and the hotel business in Russia, 2017. Pp. 344-349.
3. Maltseva V. M., Tyrina T. G. 2016. Personalization Programs in the Hospitality Industry: Sharia-Compliant Hotels. In: Yu. P. Kozhayeva, O. Yu. Zevke (eds.). Current Issues in Science: From Theory to Practice. Moscow: Russian State Social University; 27-33.
4. Marshakova-Shaykevich I. V. 2013. The Role of Bibliometrics in Assessing Research Activity in Science. Management of Large Systems (44): 210-247.